

Soil-Foundation-Structure Interaction Effects on urban scale Vulnerability Assessment

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ABSTRACT

Urban-scale seismic risk assessment is of paramount importance to identify the impact of future earthquakes in cities, to assist national authorities in risk mitigations policies as well as after seismic event emergency management. To date, a seismic risk assessment framework at a large scale is assessed considering a portfolio of fixed-base structures. It is rather clear that when structures rest on soft soil profiles the interaction between the soil, foundation, and structure (SSI) may arise. Including SSI effects in the city-scale vulnerability analysis may be challenging due to the high exposure concentration and complexity of the whole interacting system not to mention the limited amount of data on the foundation building inventory. For this reason, large-scale analyses are commonly carried out applying existing fragility curves which generally neglect SSI and may have been assessed for different soil conditions. A novel simplified methodology is proposed in this study to calculate fragility functions of structures considering the influence of SSI and local site-effects, suitable for large-scale application. An improved taxonomy defines the resulting fragility functions introducing the averaged shear-wave velocity in the top 30 m ($V_{S,30}$) as a proxy for the site and SSI effects. The outcomes of the methodological framework are adopted to estimate the risk in terms of damages incurred by the most popular building classes of Thessaloniki, Northern Greece for the Thessaloniki 1978, Mw 6.5 historical earthquake. The main findings reported herein demonstrate that the conventional way of performing risk analysis may lead affect the seismic risk estimates by a substantial margin.

Keywords: soil-structure-interaction, site-amplification, urban risk assessment

INTRODUCTION

In the last years, fragility curves have emerged as a fundamental support tool for decision-makers and stakeholders to identify the potential seismic risk and the consequences in pre- and post-earthquake management. Fragility functions of structures, especially for large-scale applications, are generally developed for fixed-base structures, thus neglecting the potential interaction with the underlying soil. The incorporation of SSI phenomena in the analysis has been generally considered beneficial in reducing the seismic demand and consequently the corresponding structural damage of non-linear systems (Ciampoli & Pinto, 1995). Additionally, in a large-scale risk framework, characterizing the soil-foundation system is considered a challenging task due to the difficulty in characterizing the whole interacting system. Despite this, in the last years, many research efforts (Sáez et al, 2011; Rajeev & Tesfamariam, 2012; Pitilakis et al, 2014; Karapetrou et al. 2015; de Silva, 2020; Petridis & Pitilakis, 2020; Cavalieri et al, 2020; Brunelli et al, 2022) recognized that neglecting such effects may lead to an underestimation of seismic risk. Even though the results of such studies provided the scientific community with valuable knowledge for a site-specific vulnerability assessment, the reliability at a large scale needs to be further exploited. Not all the possible soil-foundation-structure systems have been covered so far, making the existing fragility functions accounting for SSI

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inadequate for large-scale analyses. Moreover, for the extensive applications, soil conditions may be considered in the seismic hazard assessment adopting either code- or research-based amplification factors or through very advanced models (physical-numerical simulations, microzonation analysis). Still, they might not have been correctly considered in the fragility curves.

To this end, this study presents a systematic methodology for estimating fragility curves of different classes of buildings considering SSI and local site effects, applicable to different reinforced concrete and masonry buildings for a great variety of soil-foundation scenarios that can be encountered in an urban environment. The resulting fragility functions are defined on the base of an improved taxonomy which introduces the $V_{S,30}$ as a proxy for SSI and site effects. To prove the proposed methodology's feasibility, we estimate damages incurred by the most popular building classes of Thessaloniki, Northern Greece for the Mw 6.5 historical earthquake.

METHODOLOGY

This section introduces a new methodology to assess fragility functions for different building classes founded on shallow or embedded foundations considering SSI and site-amplification. It is well known that assessing the influence of SSI effects in an urban environment may be demanding, starting from the definition of the main features defining the whole interacting system.

Figure. 1 Flow chart of the proposed methodology for the fragility assessment of structures considering SSI and site-effects at an urban scale.

With this in mind, the applicability of the devised methodology is taught to be based on globally available input data regarding the soil parameters, the foundation, and the building taxonomy, thus making it easily applicable for risk assessment at different cities. Nevertheless, if available, detailed local information on the foundation building inventory and site conditions from microzonation studies will provide fragility estimates with a lower degree of uncertainty. To further promote its implementation, all the analyses are conceived to be implemented in the open-source OpenSees software (Mazzoni et al., 2006). In Fig. 1 is outlined the whole methodological framework where each step is briefly described below:

- Step 1: The flowchart starts with the definition of the input parameters. A large set of input ground motions mostly recorded on outcropping rock/firm soil is selected to consider the randomness of ground motions formally. To include local site-effects and determine the foremost features of the soil in the SSI modelling is necessary to define representative soil profiles that should be conceived to cover all the different soil types. To reduce the computational effort, the structure is taught to be modeled following the equivalent single degree of freedom (ESDoF) system approximation (D'Alayla et al., 2014). This ESDoF is placed on translational and vertical springs and dashpots simulating the compliance of the foundation subsoil using the Beam-on-Nonlinear-Winkler-Foundation (BNWF) concept (NIST, 2012).
- Step 2: The modification of the selected records due to the local site-effects is quantified by performing 1D numerical simulations of seismic site response performed. Ground motions computed at the

previous step are selected as input at the base of the compliant base model to perform all the dynamic cloud analyses (Jalayer et al. et al, 2017). Then, for structures resting on surface foundations, the free-field motion is directly applied as input for the dynamic analyses (di Laora & de Sanctis, 2013). Whereas for embedded foundations, the free-field motion is further modified to consider the kinematic interaction before being applied at the base of the superstructure. Indeed, to further reduce the computational burden, the problem is solved through the substructure approach, thus avoiding proposing procedures too structure-site-foundation-dependent.

- Step 3: The statistical treatment of the results allows calculating the probability of exceeding four different limit states (namely slight, moderate, extensive, and complete damage state) given the intensity measure, IM. An improved fragility model, namely Modified Cloud analysis, MCA (Jalayer et al., 2017), is adopted herein to compute fragility functions which formally considers the collapse-inducing records. Collapse cases are defined in literature as the input motions causing structural collapse and/or reaching dynamic instability due to large deformations. This method effectively characterizes the fragility of compliant base structures since collapse cases are more likely to occur when SSI effects are significant.

Finally, one of the novelties of the proposed approach is to provide fragility functions classified according to the averaged shear-wave velocity in the top 30 m ($V_{S,30}$), conceived in this work as a proxy for the site and SSI effects. The advantage of this revised taxonomy is the possibility to link the so calculated fragility functions directly with real site conditions that may be defined on the base of $V_{S,30}$ maps derived, just to mention a few, from detailed in situ analyses or from proxies such as the slope (Allen & Wald, 2007) or the local geology (Forte et al., 2017).

CASE STUDY

The section presents an application of the proposed methodology to perform the seismic risk assessment of the city of Thessaloniki, aiming to prove the feasibility of the proposed framework. Seven different representative clayey soil profiles were modelled in the OpenSees software. The same approach can be easily applied for a sandy soil profile, nevertheless, recent works (Pitilakis & Petridis, 2022) on the topic recognized no important differences in the final fragility curves. The selected soil profiles were conceived considering different average propagation velocities of the shear waves within the first 30m of soil depth, $V_{S,30}$ (i.e., ranging from 150 to 450 m/s as reported in Table 1), thus of the soil types B, C and D according to EC8 classification (CEN, 2005). A simplified distribution is considered in this study to describe the distribution of the soil shear modulus of G with depth as follows:

$$V_S(z) = V_{S,z=30} \left(\left(\frac{V_{S,z=0}}{V_{S,z=30}} \right)^{\frac{1}{a}} + \frac{z}{30} \left(1 - \left(\frac{V_{S,z=0}}{V_{S,z=30}} \right)^{\frac{1}{a}} \right) \right)^a \quad (1)$$

where z stands for the depth measured from the soil surface, while $V_{S,z=0}$ and $V_{S,z=30}$ are the soil shear modulus at the ground surface and a depth of 30 meters, respectively. The $V_{S,z=0}$ and $V_{S,z=30}$ are randomly selected to ensure a $V_{S,30}$ equal to the values reported in Table 1. Moreover, to guarantee stiffness parameters vary in the range embedded in the empirical relationships (d'Onofrio & Silvestri 2001) the coefficient a is assumed equal to 0.25. Some restraint were adopted for the random selection of the parameters as ensuring values not unrealistically approach zero values near ground surface and guarantee stiffness parameters vary in the range embedded in the empirical relationships relating the small strain stiffness, G_0 , and the geostatic stress state and history, i.e. according to soil index and state properties (d'Onofrio & Silvestri 2001) To this aim, the a coefficient was selected equal to 0.25.

Table 1 Main soil parameters selected to characterize the soil profile

$V_{S,30}$ (m/s)	150	180	250	300	360	400	450	>800
$V_{S,z=2B}$ (m/s)	122	147	203	244	293	325	366	>800
T_{SSI} (s)	0.57	0.56	0.54	0.54	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.52
T_{SSI}/T_{FB}	1.10	1.08	1.04	1.04	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.00

The foundation features, the aspect ratio H/B (where B is the characteristic foundation half-length) and the structure-to-soil relative inertia, δ , are defined as $H/B=2$, and $\delta=0.05$, after a literature review of previous studies on SSI available for the case study of Thessaloniki, northern Greece (Karapetrou et al. 2015; Petridis & Ptilakis, 2020). These interaction parameters allow defining the whole foundation system, which is reduced to an equivalent rectangular surface foundation of length $2B$. It is worth mentioning at this stage, that this approximated foundation can be considered more representative of shallow footings, grid or interconnected beams rather than independent footings. The stiffness used to calibrate the springs is selected as a function of a shear wave velocity mobilized considering an interaction volume equal to the total foundation length ($V_{S,z=2B}$ values reported in Table 1). For this showcase application, results for one building class representative of mid-rise regularly infilled structures designed with low-code prescriptions are selected from the Thessaloniki exposure (namely CR-LFINF-DUL- H4 following the GEM taxonomy, D’Ayala et al., 2014). Table 1 reports the elongated period for all the SSI models (i.e. same structural typology endowed with different BNWF models considered). The non-linear behavior of the ESDoF representing the superstructure is defined from the nonlinear backbone curve (capacity curve) available in the literature for different building classes (Martins & Silva, 2020).

Fragility functions are evaluated in terms of pseudo-spectral acceleration at elongated and fundamental periods for the flexible- and fixed-base structure, respectively (T_{SSI} and T_{FB} listed Table 1). The selected intensity measure refers to the analysis input records (i.e., recorded on rock/stiff soil). The outcomes of the proposed methodology are fragility functions developed for the selected building class considering the influence of SSI and site amplification. Fig. 2 compares the fragility functions for the analyzed building class accounting for different hypotheses on $V_{S,30}$ and for all the predefined limit states.

Figure. 2 Comparison between fragility functions in terms of $Sa(T)_R$ developed for one reference building class, i.e., CR-LFINF-DUL-H4 considering SSI and site-effects for a BNWF system characterized by $H/B=2$, $\delta=0.05$ and (a) $V_{S,30}=180m/s$ and (b) $V_{S,30}=300m/s$, (c) $V_{S,30}=450m/s$ and (b) and $V_{S,30}>800m/s$ for the same structure but fixed at its base.

All in all, the result of the analyses for the flexible foundations, i.e., considering SSI and site-effects (Fig. 2 a, b, and c), produce a shift to the left of the fragility curves compared to the fixed-base case (Fig. 2 d), thus resulting into an increase of the structural fragility. The fragility shift is more pronounced for very soft soil

profiles, see Fig. 2 a, developed for the virtual soil profile corresponding to $V_{s,30}$ 180 m/s, compared to Fig. 2 c for $V_{s,30}$ 450 m/s. For the sake of completeness, the fragility parameters, mainly median value and standard deviation, are listed in Table 2 for all the annualized configurations, i.e., following the fixed-base assumption and considering the compliance of the underlying soil for all the soil profiles listed in Table 1.

Table 2 Fragility parameters, i.e. median value, η , and standard deviation, σ , considering SSI and SE or FB assumptions for all the defined limit states.

	SSI + SE														FB	
	$V_{s,30}=150$		$V_{s,30}=180$		$V_{s,30}=250$		$V_{s,30}=300$		$V_{s,30}=360$		$V_{s,30}=400$		$V_{s,30}=450$		$V_{s,30}=800$	
	η	σ														
<i>SD</i>	0.05	0.52	0.05	0.52	0.06	0.48	0.08	0.48	0.10	0.47	0.10	0.47	0.12	0.47	0.16	0.50
<i>MD</i>	0.27	0.53	0.27	0.53	0.32	0.49	0.38	0.48	0.42	0.48	0.44	0.47	0.49	0.48	0.61	0.50
<i>ED</i>	0.55	0.53	0.55	0.53	0.60	0.48	0.71	0.49	0.75	0.48	0.79	0.48	0.86	0.49	1.01	0.50
<i>CD</i>	0.82	0.55	0.82	0.55	0.82	0.47	1.02	0.50	1.05	0.50	1.10	0.49	1.20	0.50	1.32	0.50

Risk Analysis

Results of the proposed approach, i.e. fragility functions accounting for SSI and site effects, are implemented within the destructive Mw 6.5 1978 Volvi earthquake scenario to address the distribution of damages inferred by the main structural typology of the Thessaloniki building stock.

For this purpose, ground motion scenarios are computed using the OpenQuake platform (Pagani et al., 2014). The main features of the rupture model are reported in Table 3 (for detailed information the reader is referred to the work published by Smerzini & Pitilakis, (2017;2018)). The GMPEs model proposed by Akkar & Boomer (2010), is employed herein to compute the ground motion field in terms of spectral acceleration for all the periods listed in Table 1. As mentioned above, the seismic fragilities including site-effects and SSI are expressed in terms of intensity measure with reference to the analysis input records (i.e. as recorded on rock/stiff soil) hence the ground motion field refers to the outcropping bedrock. As already stated, all the fragility functions are classified according to the averaged shear-wave velocity in the top 30 m ($V_{s,30}$). The so-classified fragility function is linked with real site conditions defined on the base of a detailed measured $V_{s,30}$ maps for the Thessaloniki municipality (Riga et al, 2020; Anastasiadis et al, 2002).

Table 3 Kinematic source parameters for the simulation of the 1978 Volvi earthquake.

Mw	Hypocenter (°N, °E)	Depth	Rake	Dip
6.5	40.705; 23.266	8 Km	-70	46

The damage distribution computed following the devised methodology is compared with the classical approach for large scale risk analysis. As it is well known, classical approaches employ existing fixed-base fragility functions and include site amplification by means of amplification factors in the GMPEs. Following this approach, the scenario is computed in terms of $Sa(T=0.6s)$ considering amplification factors from measured V_s profiles in the studied area (Riga et al, 2020; Anastasiadis et al, 2002). The resulting ground motion field refers to the free surface. The fragility models developed by the Global Earthquake Model (GEM) (Martins & Silva, 2020) are adopted for this showcase comparison. It is worth mentioning that such fragility functions do not perfectly match the fixed-base fragility function of Fig. 2d, being developed for a different set of input records and a slightly different fundamental period ($T=0.6s$ instead of $T=0.52s$). Despite their large applicability, such fragility functions are poorly constrained to the real site conditions being developed considering a huge set of input ground motions. The damage distributions obtained following both the approaches in the urban area of Thessaloniki are reported in Fig. 3 concerning the slight damage state, while Fig. 4 compares the results aggregated for the whole municipality and all the considered limit states.

As displayed in Fig. 4, the selected building class experienced mainly slight damage. Nevertheless, while for fixed-base structures, the percentage of building experiencing the slight damage state is 48%, when considering the compliance of the foundation soil and site effects utilizing site response analysis, this percentage increases up to 55% (such variation can also be observed from the variation in the spatial distribution of Fig. 3). This tendency is somehow inverted for the complete damage state, which affects more fixed-base structures under

the classical risk approach. At this stage may be difficult to assess whether this can be attributed to the difference in terms of fragility functions, i.e. between the fixed-base fragility curve computed by GEM (Martins & Silva, 2020) and in this application (see Fig. 2d) or in the hazard scenario.

Despite this, it is rather clear that when considering SSI and local site-effects through site response analysis, the distribution of damages and thus the final risk may be different from the classical approach, which considers site effects employing amplification factor neglecting site-effects. The main findings of the present work demonstrate that the proposed methodology can provide a more accurate assessment of damages. It can be effectively employed to improve seismic risk studies in strategic urban areas.

Figure 3 Number of buildings experiencing the slight damage state for the same earthquake scenario, i.e. Thessaloniki 1978 earthquake Mw 6.5, considering (a) fragility functions accounting for SSI and site-effects and (b) the most simplified assumption which neglects SSI and site-effects.

Figure 4 Percentages of buildings experiencing all the predefined damage states considering (a) SSI and site effects using site response analyses and (b) neglecting SSI and considering site effects using amplification factors.

CONCLUSIONS

The main goal of this work is to propose a new methodology to include SSI and local site effects in the urban scale vulnerability assessment of structures. Hence, the presented framework is based on globally available input data where all the analyses are taught to be implemented in the OpenSees opensource software. To prove the feasibility of the proposed approach and understand the role that SSI and site-effects play on the final damage asset rather than being limited to the structural fragility assessment, we provide the reader with the applicability in the framework of an urban-scale risk assessment. To do so, we assess the distribution of damages in the Thessaloniki municipality when considering the Mw 6.5 Volvi historical earthquake. Finally, we investigate whether the proposed framework compared to the classical approach used for risk calculation may affect the seismic risk at a large scale. Comparison was made with the reference case where SSI is ignored and the site effects are assessed rather than performing 1D analyses through amplification factors. To improve the comparison the latter coefficients are defined from a very detailed knowledge of site conditions in terms of shear wave velocity $V_{s,30}$. The main results of this application lead to understanding that a more refined approach where site effects are SSI are properly taken into account may affect the overall distribution of damages.

Finally, this study encourages the adoption of SSI models in the fragility computation compared to more simplified approaches for the large-scale application to perform a correct quantification of the potential fragility estimates of cities.

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